

INTEGRATIVE LESSONS IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM AND WAYS OF THEIR USE

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Abstract: This article discusses integrative lessons in the modern education system and ways of using them. The modern education system is aimed at forming a highly educated, intellectually developed individual with a holistic understanding of the worldview and processes that represent this worldview. Today, it is most obvious that a new quality of education cannot be achieved by solving pedagogical problems using outdated methods. The introduction of subject integration into the education system has made it possible to solve the problems set before the school and society as a whole.

Key words: integrative lesson, pedagogical problems, methods and techniques, students of non-linguistic universities, modern education system.

1 Introduction

The term "integration" has become firmly established in works on pedagogy in the 80s. Originally from the Latin "integratio", which means restoration, replenishment, unification into a whole of any parts, even earlier this term was widely used in the professional vocabulary of various fields of knowledge to denote the corresponding process. "The Philosophical Encyclopedic Dictionary" develops the definition of integration, supplements it with such a concept as "the side of the development process associated with the unification into a whole of previously heterogeneous parts and elements." We find a similar definition in the "logical dictionary-reference book", which defines integration as "... unification into a whole, into a unity of any elements, restoration of any unity" [1]. In the exact sciences, integration is understood as summation over some parameter with its own weight, and the integral as "an integer value considered as the sum of its infinitely small parts." In pedagogy, integration is defined as "...the highest form of expression of the unity of goals, principles, content, and forms of organization of the process of teaching and upbringing, carried out in two cycles of education, aimed at intensifying the entire training system..."[2].

Teaching methodology is a joint activity between the teacher and the student. It is aimed at achieving certain educational goals. The choice of methods and means in teaching depends on many objects and subjects:

Depending on the role of the trainees, methods are divided into: active, passive and interactive. The reason is that the groups in which students and cadets are trained may be different. In weak groups, the "forced activity" method is used. The teacher forcibly activates the thinking and activity of students;

Active groups absorb information quickly. This knowledge is improved through the learning process. Such training can be used when students already have the basics of the necessary knowledge; this knowledge was obtained using traditional methods. Traditional and innovative methods have their own strengths, and the task of the teacher is to find reasonable use of each method depending on the lesson.

Traditional methods. Students are to a greater extent the subject of learning. The student asks questions to the teacher, questions from the teacher to the student to develop creative thinking. Individual contact is established between the teacher and the student, but not with other members of the group. Such methods are used in seminar classes and in independent work. Experience shows that such methods activate the teacher, and the student becomes passive [5].

Interactive methods. By teaching others, we learn ourselves (Seneca) - this method involves joint learning between the teacher and the student. The teacher acts only as a more experienced organizer of the learning process. Trainees are immersed in an atmosphere of cooperation and solve problems in the optimal way. Interactive methods create an environment and atmosphere for the manifestation and demonstration of their knowledge, skills and qualities. During the learning process, all students interact with each other, exchange information, and solve problems together.

Interactive methods require the teacher to carefully plan the work. He needs to give the participants time for preliminary preparation; read, think through, complete tasks independently. It should be noted that the interactive method allows students to demonstrate their individual qualities, such as; leadership, organizational and public speaking skills [3; 4].

The traditional method allows mainly knowledge and understanding, while the interactive method covers all cognitive levels. It requires a change in the approach to learning on the part of both the teacher and the students.

Thus, integration is a deep interpenetration, fusion, as far as possible, in one educational material of generalized knowledge in a particular area. Integration is the highest level of embodiment of interdisciplinary connections, which have been widely studied by teachers, psychologists, and methodologists. An indicator of a student's mental development is the transfer of knowledge from one subject to another, which characterizes the productivity of cognitive activity. Transfer consists of interdisciplinary generalization of the known and synthesis of new, generalized knowledge. Interdisciplinary connections in teaching introduce elements of creativity into the student's mental activity, as well as elements of reproduction and search, manifested in cognitive activity. It should be noted that integrated lessons are built on the basis of interdisciplinary connections, which in turn activate students' interest in the subject.

2 Experimental results and their discussion

In Russian language lessons we work in small groups. This provides an opportunity to practice collaboration and interpersonal communication skills. In small groups there is a high level of information exchange; students have different levels of training. Someone absorbs information well and quickly and actively gets involved in work. Another student may be passive and weak. In such cases, active people help passive ones, solve problems together, and exchange information. It is helpful to maintain a stable group composition so that participants can achieve mastery of group work.

In small groups, the teacher should be an “observer” and analyze how group members cope with problems that arise during the work. To observe, you need to pay attention to the following aspects:

These aspects help to analyze the effectiveness of work, discuss the meaning of the rules of work in a group. The use of interactive methods in small groups requires certain changes in the form of classes. The introduction of these methods makes it possible for both the teacher and the student to better understand the program. Initially, you should use simple methods - brainstorming, blitz surveys, mosaics, etc. There are methodological rules for working in groups:

We always talk about the joint work of two or more teachers in preparing and conducting an integrated lesson. However, such lessons can also be conducted by one teacher who is proficient in the material of the integrated discipline. Such situations are becoming the norm today. The main feature of an integrated lesson is that such a lesson is based on one subject, which is the main one. The other subjects integrated with it help to study its connections and processes more broadly, to understand the essence of the subject being studied more deeply, to understand the connections with real life and the possibility of applying the acquired

knowledge in practice. Such lessons cannot be conducted often, as they lose their novelty and interest. In turn, these lessons allow the teacher to reduce the time for studying individual topics, eliminate duplication of material in different subjects, and pay more attention (in various forms) to the goals that the teacher highlights at a given moment of training (development of speech, thinking, spelling vigilance, creativity). Integrated lessons relieve students' fatigue and overexertion by switching from one type of activity to another. In addition, one of the mandatory and basic requirements of integrated teaching is to increase the role of students' independence, because integration inevitably expands the subject matter of the material being studied, necessitating a deeper analysis and generalization of phenomena, the range of which increases due to other subjects. Is it possible for schoolchildren to independently study such a volume of material? Students will cope with such work only if they have mastered the techniques of research activities and know how to properly organize their time.

For example, when analyzing the poem "Sail" by M.Yu. Lermontov, cadets can work according to a set schedule, that is, we divide the group into two subgroups, one subgroup reveals the theme, the other subgroup reveals the nature of this work. Each subgroup will offer its own options, give examples, comment and defend its point of view. In conclusion, the "expert", that is, the teacher, makes the final decision. This will be a discussion lesson. A good teacher understands the state and mood of his cadets. Taking this into account, he attracts additional sources, teaches his cadets to work independently, actively participate, and support each other.

Subgroups should have strong and weak cadets. This will be a joint work, the strong help the weak and the number of participants should be equal.

4 Conclusions

Thus, the main goal of classes using interactive methods is to feel like a team solving problems together and to realize mutual responsibility. And for a teacher, the main achievement is to create a favorable atmosphere, respect, support and an optimal amount of knowledge. Visual aids should be used in lessons. Such aids can be diagrams, slides, tables, video recordings and audio recordings. There is a good principle: "It is better to see once than to hear a hundred times." When using visual aids, it is necessary to comment on them. It is necessary to prepare a lesson so that visual aids are accessible to everyone, are thought out

expediently, and with the help of technical means it would be possible to show slides and presentations. There are visual aids that can be demonstrated during a presentation. Analyzing the above, we can say the following, an integrated approach to teaching subjects in the humanities has a number of positive aspects.

Firstly, in integrated lessons, students develop and consolidate universal learning activities (cognitive, communicative, personal and regulatory).

Secondly, in integrated lessons, students are given the opportunity to look at related subjects from a different angle. This leads to an increase in the interest of students.

Thirdly, in the process of integrated lessons, students develop a holistic view of the world, which is manifested in the need to study the subjects that make up the school curriculum.

But, along with this, the integrated approach has its drawbacks. The main one is the complexity of organizing integrated lessons and excessive saturation, "overload" of the lesson. In addition, when drawing up a calendar and thematic planning, subject teachers must jointly develop a work plan for conducting integrated lessons. Thus, integrated lessons contribute to the formation of a holistic picture of the world in children, understanding the connections between phenomena in nature, society and the world as a whole. They develop the potential of students, encourage them to actively explore the world around them, to understand cause-and-effect relationships, to develop logical thinking and communication skills. These are health-preserving lessons: they relieve fatigue and stress in students by switching to various types of activities. Finally, integration provides an opportunity for self-realization, creativity of the teacher, and the disclosure of his or her abilities. Integrated learning really creates new conditions for the activities of the teacher and students, since it is based on cooperation and interaction of several teachers. Relationships between teachers and students are also built in a new way, which contributes to students' self-expression, their greater emancipation in the classroom and the creation of an atmosphere of community. And summing up the work done, I would like to say that we must think about the fact that the integration of subjects in a modern school is a real need of the time, necessary for all those interested in the formation of a comprehensively developed personality, as well as for all those involved in issues of basic pedagogical education.

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